

**CLASSIFICATION OF VOICES IN UZBEK, GERMAN AND ENGLISH
PHONETICS BY OPENING THE MOUTH, LIFT RISE AND LAB
PARTICIPATION**

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ANNOTATION

The purpose of this article is to classify the most important and general features of vowels in the phonemics of Uzbek, English and German languages, ie the opening of the mouth, the rise of the tongue and the presence of the lips. Numerous studies have been conducted by a number of linguists on the study of phonetics. Many changes took place in all three languages before the current single and phonemic-systematic pattern. As an example, this article explains the general classifications according to the classification of vowels in English, Uzbek and German, and highlights their differences and similarities. In this case, the object of study of the article were the vowels in the phonemics of Uzbek, English and German. The subject of the work is the classification of vowels in the phonetics of these three languages according to their general characteristics. Materials were collected mainly from phonetic sources of 3 languages. Theoretical sources, scientific works, textbooks and monographs were used as a theoretical source.

Keywords: phonetics, sound, vowels, classification, analysis by opening the mouth, analysis by language, lip participation, labial, non-labial, monoftong, diphthong, diphthongoid.

INTRODUCTION

The first President I.A Karimov said, "Our efforts in the field of science, as well as our scientific work and achievements, should be measured by the most advanced criteria in the world" (1, B-80). This opinion of the First President is directly related to the field of linguistics. Science is always evolving and evolving. Today it is gaining momentum at an unprecedented rate.

In today's global world, there are countless languages and dialects. But not all of them are widespread or survive. The fact that languages are not dead languages depends on how well they are studied, composed and, of course, the number of speakers. Among the linguistic departments of each language, first of all, its phonetic, that is, the analysis of sounds and letters, is one of the most important.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Phonetics is derived from the Greek word "phone", which is a branch of linguistics. It studies the phonetic parts of language - speech sounds, syllables, words, phrases and intonation. Phonetics, as the most important part of the science of language, has both practical and theoretical significance. That is, without a complete study of the phonetic structures of language, it is difficult to imagine its grammatical forms, phrases and sentences. It is useless to study its lexical and grammatical structure before studying its phonetic structure. The role of phonetics in the study of foreign languages is also very important. Because not all languages are the same, for example, vowels in German are not available in English or Uzbek.

Each language is unique - it has its own characteristics. But you can also see the similarities. Throughout this article, you will witness the analysis of 3 different phonetics of exactly 3 different languages - their similarities and differences.

According to it, the classification of Uzbek, German, English vowels according to the opening of the mouth, the rise of the tongue and the presence of the lips was taken as an analysis. Because in the process of studying the phonetics of these languages, a number of analyzes and explanations were found that the above features can be both different and common for all three languages. The common denominator is that in Uzbek, German, English phonetics there is also a classification according to the above features, but in different forms. That is, they differ radically in internal analysis and characteristics.

In this scientific article, separate paragraphs have been allocated for the analysis of the phonetics of each language. Comments and analysis are performed in the following order:

1. On the phonetics of Uzbek vowels
2. On the phonetics of German vowels
3. On the phonetics of English vowels

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The symbols that form the basis for the classification of consonant phonemes are not the same as the symbols that form the basis for the classification of vowel phonemes. Even in the classification of vowel phonemes of each language, we see that their signs are different.

Analysis of vowels in the phonetics of the Uzbek language by the presence of the mouth and lips.

Vowel sounds are sounds that are formed in the oral cavity without any obstruction. In the phonetics of the Uzbek language there are 30 sounds, 6 of which are vowels. There are 30 sounds in Uzbek language, 6 of them are vowels. In fact, in the literature of Uzbek linguistics there are 3 different classifications of vowels:

- 1- instead of appearing
- 2- According to the degree of opening of the mouth and the rise of the tongue
- 3- According to the presence of lips

There were two different approaches to the emergence of vowels. In Approach 1, the place of their appearance is recognized, mainly horizontal movement. In approach 2, the sign of the appearance of vowels is rejected, so the classification of vowels according to this sign is unfounded (2, B-77-80).

Professor Umarov. E Uzbeks ask whether they really pronounce the above vowels in front of or behind the tongue, that is, speak in front of or behind the tongue, and state that they should answer "no" without hesitation. Professor Umarov.E in his second article shows that it is appropriate to classify vowels according to the degree of opening of the mouth and the presence of the lips (3, B-52-53).

Thus, it is expedient to classify the phonemes of modern Uzbek literary language on the basis of 2 signs:

- 1- According to the degree of opening of the mouth
- 2- According to the presence of lips

One of the most important distinguishing features of vowels in Turkic languages is the width-narrowness, that is, the degree of opening of the mouth. There are 3 stages of research in the phonetics of the Uzbek language:

Wide: a - o

Semi-wide: e - o`

Short: i - u

The reason why vowels are divided into wide, semi-wide and narrow is that when they are pronounced, the lower jaw drops or the distance of the tongue from the hard palate varies. For example, when pronouncing the first vowel, the tongue is raised to the maximum, and the lower jaw is in the same position. As a result, the airway in the oral cavity is reduced to a minimum. That is why i and u are called narrow vowels. When pronouncing the vowels a and o, the opposite happens when the vowels i and u are pronounced, and these sounds are called broad vowels. When pronouncing the sound e and o, the distance between the tongue and the hard palate is averaged relative to the situation when pronouncing the sound i and u or the sound a and o.

Another important distinguishing feature for Uzbek literary vowels is the classification of vowels according to the presence of lips.

In the Uzbek language, according to the presence of lips, vowels are divided into 2 types:

1- lips involved

2- lips not involved

Lip vowels are vowels that are formed when the lips are actively involved in pronunciation, the lips are puffy, protruding and round. They include the sounds O`, O, U.

The lips are absent or passive when the non-lips are pronounced. Such sounds include A, E, I.

A number of problems have arisen when linguists have classified vowels according to the presence of lips, and they have been discussed and resolved. In other words, there are different opinions about the origin of vocal sounds and the degree of lip. However, the following opinion of A.Abduazizov can be an answer and a solution to a number of questions:

"As a result of both influences (internal and external), the phoneme a has diverged, that is, divided into 2 phonemes."

According to Ye. D Polivanov's formula a: b - c, that is, the element c is divided into elements a and b. As a result, in Uzbek vocalism all pre-vowels i, e, a are not labeled, and all back vowels o, u, o are labeled and have two equally symmetrical groups.

In German phonetics, the level of language development and classification according to the presence of lips in pronunciation.

There are 18 vowels in German phonetics, 15 of which are monophthong and 3 are diphthong.

Monophthongs are sounds that the articulatory organs do not change from beginning to end when articulating: [a:] - [a], [e:] - [ɛ:] - [ɛ], [i:] - [i], [u:] - [u], [o:] - [ɔ], [y:] [y], [ø:] [æ].

When diphthongs are pronounced, the organs of speech move from one state to another. They are: [ao], [æ], [ø].

In German phonetics, vowels are divided into 3 groups according to the degree of development of the language:

- 1 - high rise
- 2 - medium rise
- 3 - lower rise

When high-pitched vowels are pronounced, the tongue rises towards the palate. High-pitched vowels include [i:] - [i], [u:] - [u], [y:] [y].

In the pronunciation of middle vowels, the tongue rises in the middle position: [e:] - [ɛ:] - [ɛ], [o:] - [ɔ], [ø:] [æ].

The lower rising vowels are pronounced as a result of the middle part of the tongue rising slightly towards the palate: [a:] - [a]

In German phonetics, as in Uzbek phonetics, vowels are divided into 2 groups according to the presence of lips, but their classification is slightly different. Depending on the presence of the lips, there are vocal sounds with and without lips.

When lip sounds are uttered, the lips move forward. There are 4 types of labling:

1. Strong lip - [u:] - [y];
2. The lips are slightly protruding and rounded - [o:], [ø]
3. With the lips involved, they may not protrude forward - [æ], [y:]
4. Weak lips - [o] - [u]

The lips are not actively involved in the pronunciation of unvoiced vowels, they are pulled to the side and are in a neutral position: [i:] - [i], [e:] - [ɛ:] - [ɛ] [a:] - [a]

The classification of German vowels is more complicated than in Uzbek. However, the features of the discussion were only the degree of elevation of the tongue and the type of involvement of the lips.

Classification of vowels in English phonetics according to the degree of language elevation and the presence of lips.

There are 20 vowels in the phonetics of English vowels, of which 10 are monophthong, 8 are diphthong and 2 are diphthongoid. In the above information we talked about what is monophthong and diphthong.

Monophthongs in English: [i] [e] [æ] [a:] [o] [o:] [U] [ʌ] [ə:] [ə]

Diphthongs in English: [ei] [ai] [oi] [au] [eu] [iə] [ɛə] [uə]

Diphthongoids are sounds in which the articulation is slightly pronounced, but the difference between the starting point and the end is not as great as in diphthongs: [i:] [u:]

In English, we will consider the classification of vowels according to the rise of the tongue and the movement of the lips.

As the tongue moves up and down in the mouth, it can rise at different heights toward the roof of the mouth. According to this feature, they are of 3 types:

- Closed;
- Open;
- Medium.

A vowel sound is said to be closed when the front or back of the tongue rises high toward the palate. Because the opening of the mouth, where the closed vowels are pronounced, is narrow. Such sounds include [i:] [i] [u] [u:].

When the front or back of the tongue is as low as possible, open vowels are pronounced in the mouth. That is, the degree of opening of the mouth is wide: [æ] [a:] [o] [o:].

Medium-wide vowels are pronounced when the upper part of the tongue occupies an intermediate position between closed and open. [e] [ʌ] [ə:] [ə] - these are medium-wide vowels.

Another important feature of vowels in English is the classification of lip movements. When pronouncing vocal sounds, the lips are divided into 2 states:

- Round
- It was not round

If, when pronouncing a vowel, the lips are connected to each other, and the gap between them is larger and rounder, the vowels pronounced in a round position are called: [o] [o:] [u] [u:]

If the movement of the lips during pronunciation is neutral or diffuse, they are called unvoiced vowels in a round position. They are: [i:] [i] [e] [æ] [a:] [ʌ] [ə:] [ə].

The classification of vowels in English phonetics is similar to that in German, but they are radically different in terms of internal features and structure.

SUMMARY

In conclusion, the fact that each language has its own phonetics is a guarantee of long-term prosperity of the language. While studying this article, you can get the following analysis and conclusions:

1. The phonetics of each language is different. There may be some similarities, but they are not the same.
2. In Uzbek linguistics, the classification of vowels was initially divided into 3 stages, but after several discussions and analyzes, it was found that only the degree of opening of the mouth and the participation of the lips were important.
3. The phonetics of German vowels are theoretically similar to English, but the conditions for their internal structure and criteria are different.
4. The classification of English vowels according to the degree of ascent of the language is similar to the classification of Uzbek vowels according to the degree of opening of the mouth.

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